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Stress dependent shear wave splitting and permeability in fractured porous rock

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ABSTRACT

It is well known that shear wave propagates slower across than parallel to a fracture, and as a result, a travelling shear wave splits into two directions when it encounters a fracture. Shear wave splitting and permeability of porous rock core samples having single fracture were experimentally investigated using a high pressure triaxial cell, which can measure seismic shear wave velocities in two directions mutually perpendicular to the sample axis in addition to the longitudinal compressive wave velocity. A single fracture was created in the samples using a modified Brazilian Split Test device, where the cylindrical sample edges were loaded on two diametrically opposite lines by sharp guillotines along the sample length. Based on tilt tests and fracture surface profilometry, the method of artificially inducing tensile fracture in the sample was found to create repeatable fracture surfaces and morphologies. Seismic velocities of the fractured samples were determined under different levels of stress confinement and fracture shear displacement or mismatch. The effective confining stress was varied from 0.5 to 55 MPa, while the fractures were mismatched by 0, 0.45 and 1.00 mm. The degree of mismatching of the fracture surfaces in the core samples was evaluated using the Joint Matching Coefficient (*JMC*). Shear wave splitting, as measured by the difference in the magnitudes of shear wave velocities parallel and perpendicular to the fracture V_{s1} and V_{s2} respectively, is found to be insensitive to the degree of mismatch of the fracture joint surfaces at 2 MPa, and decreased and approached zero as the effective stress was increased. Simple models for the stress and *JMC* dependent shear wave splitting and fractured rock permeability were developed based on the experimental observations. The effects of the Joint wall Compressive Strength (*JCS*), *JMC*, and stress on the stress dependency of joint aperture were discussed in terms of mechanical and hydraulic response. Finally, a useful relationship between

fracture rock permeability and shear wave splitting was found after normalization by using *JMC*.

Keywords: Fractured rock · Sandstone · Stress dependency · Shear wave splitting · Wave velocity · Permeability · Fracture stiffness · Elastic modulus

1. Introduction

Understanding of the geology, structure and fluid flow characteristic of fractured reservoirs is important in petroleum engineering, ground water resource utilization and environmental engineering. One of the most extensively used techniques to obtain information on the geologic structure of rock formations is by the use of seismic velocity measurements. Seismic surveys can be used to obtain maps of the distribution of seismic velocities in a rock formation and interfaces between rock units. Seismic data can then be correlated to fractured rock mass hydro-mechanical properties. Rock masses are generally heterogeneous and contain different types of discontinuities including bedding planes, joints and fractures. As a result, rock mass elastic behavior is expected to be anisotropic, and it turn, seismic wave propagation should be direction-dependent as well.

The most pronounced phenomenon of direction-dependent seismic wave propagation is “shear wave splitting” or “seismic birefringence” when a shear wave encounters a discontinuity. Shear wave splitting in earth and rock materials has been observed in the field and laboratory (Crampin et al. 1990; Gao et al. 1995; Zhang et al. 2000; Miller and Savage 2001; Cochran et al. 2006; Margheriti et al. 2006). Shear wave splitting is caused by anisotropies related to rock microstructure and/or induced by anisotropic stresses. Shear waves entering in an anisotropic rock split into two orthogonal directions and propagate at different speeds as illustrated in Figure 1 (Martin and Davis 1987). The polarization of shear waves propagating vertically underground occurs in a way that the faster split wave polarizes in

almost parallel direction to the maximum horizontal stress (Gao and Crampin 2008). Shear wave splitting is used to explore the degree of anisotropy by use of seismic survey. Shear wave splitting provides directly interpretable information about the progress of non-linear dynamic deformation in the deep interior of the microcracked earth (Crampin et al. 2018). In turn, measurements on degree of anisotropy are used to a better understanding of fracturing intensity, and fracture orientations and alignments (Tillotson et al. 2011). More importantly, the information gathered on fracture density also offers good indication of areas of increased permeability within a reservoir.

Fractures play important roles in the behavior of fractured rock masses. In turn, fracture hydro-mechanical response is dependent on many factors including fracture morphology, stress level, degree of closure and shear displacement, and fracture length (Pratt et al. 1974; Barton et al. 1985). Fracture permeability is often described by using the parallel plate model assuming fracture walls are represented by two smooth parallel plates separated by given aperture. Solving the Navier–Stokes equations for flow in the parallel plate model provides the cubic law (Witherspoon et al. 1980). However, the Navier–Stokes equations cannot be solved for flow along more realistic geometries representing rough fracture walls in closed form (Zimmerman and Bodvarsson 1996). Real fractures have rough surfaces, thus, the equivalent hydraulic aperture of rock fracture is different from the mechanical aperture. Previously proposed empirical models convert the mechanical aperture to the equivalent hydraulic aperture by using parameters quantifying joint surface roughness as discussed below.

Most studies on fracture hydro-mechanical behavior are based on joints with initially matching asperities. The hydro-mechanical behavior of unmatched joints or fractures is much more complicated. Bandis et al. (1983) pointed out, for instance, that the difference of joint normal stiffness between the interlocked (matched) and mismatched joints can be significant depending on the amount of joint opening and joint wall strength. Approaches different from

modeling matched joints are needed in modeling unmatched fracture hydro-mechanical behavior. One of the few approaches in modeling of unmatched fractures was proposed by Zhao (Zhao 1997a) who introduced the Joint Matching Coefficient (*JMC*) to quantify the degree of mismatching of rock fractures. When $JMC = 1$, the fracture is completely matched and the highest shear resistance is obtained (Zhao 1997b). In such highly matched joint, a small degree of mismatching can cause significant reduction of shear resistance. In the coupled measurement of fracture shear-flow behavior by Xiong et al. (2011), the hydraulic transmissivity of a joint is observed to become highly sensitive to the shear displacement immediately after start of fracture dilation. As the *JMC* value decreases, the contact area becomes smaller and shear resistance of the fracture decreases. Fracture hydraulic conductivity also increases significantly as fractures become dilated with increasing mismatch and decreasing *JMC*. When $JMC = 0$, the joint is completely mismatched. Various geological processes such as weathering can result in the reduction of *JMC* value of natural fractures.

Despite the acknowledged importance of shear wave splitting in seismic surveys of fractured rocks, understanding of the different factors that affect shear wave splitting is still limited. Also, there is a need to improve the understanding of the link between shear wave splitting and fractured rock mass permeability. In this paper, the effects of stress level and the degree of joint matching on shear wave splitting and permeability in fractured core samples of sandstone are experimentally studied. To the Authors' knowledge, this is the first systematic experimental study investigating the effect of joint mismatching on shear wave splitting behavior as well as permeability by using carefully-prepared fractured samples. Empirical models on shear wave splitting as function of effective stress, and the fractured rock permeability as function of effective stress, the Joint wall Compressive Strength *JCS* (Barton and Choubey 1977), and *JMC* are proposed based on the experimental data. The effects of stress, *JCS*, and *JMC* on shear wave splitting and fractured rock permeability are discussed. A

useful relationship to relate the shear wave splitting to the fractured rock permeability is found after the discussion.

2. Test Material and Procedures

2.1 Fractured core sample preparation and fracture surface characterization

The tested core samples were obtained from a block of Berea sandstone. The 38.1 mm diameter core samples were fractured along the longitudinal axis at two diametrically opposite locations by using two sharp loading wedges generating indirect tensile stress in the sample as shown in Fig. 2. Typical joint surface profiles traced from the induced fracture surface by using a profilometer are shown in Figure 3. The Joint Roughness Coefficient (*JRC*) of the created fractures was also determined by carrying out tilt tests (Barton et al. 1985). The induced fractures have comparable roughness with *JRC* values in the range of 6.5 ± 0.1 . Based on the tilt tests and fracture surface profilometry, the method of artificially inducing tensile fracture in the sample was found to create repeatable fracture surfaces and morphologies. Barton et al. (1985) proposed the following equation to calculate the hydraulic aperture from the mechanical aperture of a fracture by the use of *JRC*:

$$d_{eh} = \frac{JRC^{2.5}}{(d_{em}/d_{eh})^2} \quad (1)$$

where d_{eh} and d_{em} are the rock joint hydraulic and mechanical apertures, respectively, expressed in microns. Eq. (1) may provide unrealistic values for $d_{eh}/d_{em} > 1$ when the fracture joint has large aperture and low *JRC* value, as pointed out by Luo et al. (2016). There exist a number of other studies attempting to find empirical models to convert the mechanical aperture to hydraulic aperture (Patir and Cheng 1978; Renshaw 1995; Zimmerman and Bodvarsson 1996; Rasouli and Hosseinian 2011; Xiong et al. 2011; Li and Jiang 2013).

The fractures in three core samples were given different shear displacements u_{fs} of 0, 0.45, and 1.00 mm. To “re-seat” the fracture to its in situ conditions and erase any initial

disturbance of fracture core sample induced by fracturing process, the core samples were compressed by applying isotropic stresses in the triaxial cell of up to 60% of the intact rock unconfined compression strength and subsequently unloaded (Barton et al. 1985). This loading/unloading cycle is repeated three times. To maintain the fracture displacement during loading/unloading cycles, aluminum alloy spacers were placed between the end face of core sample and loading piston of the core holder. The test simulates direct shear loading in a triaxial cell. The only stresses that matter are the normal stress and shear stress acting on the fracture plane. The normal stress parallel to the fracture plane has no effect on the fracture behavior and is not controlled in the direct shear test. Since the normal stress parallel to the fracture plane does not matter, the most convenient is to make it equal to the stress normal to the fracture. The mismatched joints ($JMC = 0.3$ and 0.1) are unstable and prone to slide easily. Sliding of the fracture joints is prevented by applying isotropic stresses with zero shear stress on the fracture plane in the loading/unloading cycles. It was confirmed that there is no visible sliding after the cycles. After loading/unloading cycles, the aluminum alloy spacers were removed and then the end faces were grounded to obtain flat and parallel end faces. The effect of loading/unloading cycles on the fracture roughness was investigated by performing tilt tests on the fracture joint of core sample having 0.45 mm of shear displacement after the elastic wave velocity and permeability measurements. The JRC values determined from the tilt test decreased from 6.5 to 6.2. This means that change in roughness due to compression of the unmatched fracture surfaces is not significant.

Figure 4 shows the initial fracture apertures and JMC as function of fracture surface mismatch of the three tested samples. The joint aperture is determined as the change in the sample diameter measured along the normal to the fracture surface from its intact diameter. The joint aperture increased due to fracture dilation with increasing shear displacement from 0 to 0.23 mm. The fracture aperture estimated for 0 mm-shear joint displacement sample shown

in the figure is estimated from the following empirical relation (Barton and Bakhtar,1983):

$$d_e = \frac{JRC}{5} \left(0.2 \frac{UCS}{JCS} - 0.1 \right) \quad (2)$$

where UCS is the unconfined compressive strength of the intact rock. The measured aperture value for the matched fracture is comparable with the estimated value from Eq. (2) as seen in the figure. The JMC indicates the degree of matching of the fractures and decreases with increasing shear displacement. When $JMC = 1$, the joints are completely matched. In this study, the JMC values were determined as the ratio of the total length of matching portion of the fracture profile to the whole length of the fracture profile. The JMC values were estimated to be 0.9, 0.3 and 0.1 for the fractured core samples having 0, 0.45 and 1.00 mm shear displacements. The JMC values of the tested samples are assumed to be constant through the experimental runs under triaxial stress conditions. This is because the two halves of fractured samples are isotropically confined with the rigid axial pistons fixing their relative position during loading. It was visually confirmed that the original joint matching was maintained after testing.

2.2 Test procedure

Figure 5 illustrates the arrangement of piezo-electric transducers used for the ultrasonic wave velocity measurement in the triaxial cell. The cylindrical core plugs are pressurized in a triaxial cell having 70 MPa of cell pressure capacity. The core is encased in a Viton rubber sleeve. The end-caps of the core holder are equipped with piezoelectric transducers having natural frequencies ranging from 0.25 to 1 MHz. The ultrasonic waves generated by exciting the transducers with square pulses at one end propagate the core and are received at another set of transducers at the other end. The wave signals are monitored by using an 8-bit digital oscilloscope whose bandwidth and real time sample rate are 100 MHz and $1 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Single waveform acquired in a personal computer communicating with the oscilloscope to determine

the wave travel time is average of 16 waveforms. The ultrasonic wave velocity measurement has been done by using dry core samples at 313 K of the temperature and effective stresses of up to 55 MPa. As shown in Fig. 5, triads of shear wave transducers shake one of the end caps in two individual orthogonal directions. In the center of the cap there is a compressional wave transducer. To measure shear wave splitting, the fracture joint created are aligned parallel to the one of oscillation directions (S1) of shear wave. The faster shear wave velocity V_{s1} is obtained by the triad of transducers oscillating parallel to the fracture joint. The slower velocity V_{s2} is measured by using another triad of shear wave transducers.

The permeability of core samples was measured by using saline water having 3.4% of salinity as pore fluid at 40 °C and 10 MPa of pore pressure. **The use of 3.4% brine is to simulate the pore fluid of typical saline aquifers.** The pore fluid is transmitted from a precision syringe pump capable of sending fluids into the rock core sample at flow rates ranging from 1×10^{-3} to 107 cm³/min and at pressures of up to 50 MPa. The back pressure is controlled by using another syringe pump. The differential pressure between the inlet and outlet of core sample is monitored by using a differential pressure transducer. It is a variable reluctance type transducer having $\pm 0.25\%$ of full scale accuracy which includes the effects of non-linearity, hysteresis and non-repeatability.

3. Effects of Stress and Fracture Mismatch on Shear Wave Splitting

3.1 Laboratory measurement of shear wave splitting

Figure 6 shows typical waveforms of the faster S1 and slower S2 shear waves for the fractured core sample having $JMC = 0.1$ observed at 16 MPa of effective stress. The arrival times of S1 and S2 waves are determined to be **27.45 and 28.70** μs , respectively. Figures 7, 8 and 9 show the shear wave splitting of fractured core samples having 0.9, 0.3, and 0.1 of JMC values at effective stresses of 2 to 55 MPa. Fig. 7 shows that the sample having the matched

fracture ($JMC = 0.9$) has clear shear wave splitting response. The difference between the faster and the slower wave velocities, V_{s1} and V_{s2} , becomes smaller with increasing effective stress. Shear wave splitting is observed to be negligibly small after 35 MPa. Fig. 8 indicates that for the sample having $JMC = 0.3$ with the medium degree of shear displacement (0.45 mm) shear wave splitting persists up to 40 MPa. As seen in Fig. 9, the shear wave splitting in the sample having $JMC = 0.1$ as a result of the shear maximum displacement of 1.0 mm is not clear at low stress region from 2 to 10 MPa. However, it increases at the greater stresses and persists even at the highest stress of 55 MPa. This stress dependency suggests that the lack of shear wave splitting in the low stress range equal or less than 10 MPa is not the true shape of splitting behavior of this sample. One of the possible reasons is that the measurement of V_{s1} propagating through the fractured sample is inaccurate at those stress levels.

To estimate the probable values of V_{s1} , shear wave velocity data acquired by testing an intact core sample taken from the same sandstone block are used. The characteristic curve of stress dependency of intact shear wave velocity V_s is determined by normalizing V_s by the maximum velocity observed at 55 MPa of the highest effective stress condition V_{smax} . The probable V_{s1} of the fractured samples are calculated by multiplying the stress-dependent factor V_s/V_{smax} by the maximum V_{s1} value observed at 55 MPa for each sample. The estimated V_{s1} values of the individual samples are plotted with the cross plots in Figs. 7, 8, and 9, respectively. In Fig. 8, a very good agreement is observed between the measured and estimate values of V_{s1} over the most test stress range. In the matched fracture sample shown in Fig. 7, the estimated V_{s1} values suggests that the true V_{s1} is higher than the measured at stresses from 2 to 6 MPa. For the most sheared sample shown in Fig. 9, the deviation of the measured V_{s1} values from the estimated ones becomes significant at the stresses less than 10 MPa. However, the agreements between the measured and estimated values are great at the higher stress levels in

the both samples. These agreements as well as the quite high agreement observed in Fig. 8 demonstrates the appropriateness of the estimation procedure for the tested samples.

The appropriateness of the estimation can be verified based on a theoretical framework proposed by Pyrak-Nolte et al. (1987). In a non-welded fracture joint, the joint walls decouple when the wave frequency is higher than fracture specific frequency given as

$$\omega_c = \sqrt{\kappa/\rho c} \quad (3)$$

where κ is fracture specific stiffness, ρ is the density of rock, and c is the phase velocity in the rock (Pyrak-Nolte et al. 1992). The theoretical analysis predicted that two types of fracture wave propagate (Pyrak-Nolte and Cook 1987). At high frequency or low contact stiffness, the fracture wave velocities approach to the Rayleigh wave velocity (Pyrak-Nolte et al. 1992). The fracture-specific stiffness increases with the normal contact force. As the wave frequency decreases or stiffness increases, the fracture wave velocity increases from the Rayleigh wave velocity and approaches to the shear wave velocity of the intact rock. This theoretical framework suggests that the splitting parameter should be higher at lower stress condition. For the most mismatched joint sample ($JMC = 0.1$), using the observed V_{s1} –stress curve as the true shape of body shear wave would derive splitting behavior contradicting the theoretical prediction when the stress is less than 10 MPa. In the latter data analyses and discussions, the estimated values are used as V_{s1} for all the tested fracture samples without notice. It can be generally seen that the shear wave splitting becomes less pronounced as the effective stress increases.

Figure 10 summarizes the effects of JMC and effective stress on the degree of shear wave splitting quantified as the slowness of shear wave propagation due to the macro-fracture presence normalized by the faster shear wave velocity. The dependency of shear wave splitting on JMC can be clearly observed in the figure. The initial values of shear wave splitting parameter of core samples having $JMC = 0.9, 0.3$ and 0.1 at 2 MPa of effective stress are 7.2%,

7.4% and 6.8%, respectively. Contrary to expectations, the shear displacement on fracture does not affect the initial splitting parameter value. In all the samples, the splitting parameter decreases with stress, but the stress dependencies are different depending on the JMC value. It is seen that the splitting parameter drops more sharply at a lower stress level as the JMC value decreases. The splitting parameter of the most unmatched fracture quantified as $JMC = 0.1$ shows the significant drop from 6.7% to 3.1% due to the small stress increase from 3 to 8 MPa. After 8 MPa, the splitting parameter declines gradually with effective stress. The splitting does not disappear even at 55 MPa.

On the other hand, the matched fracture sample having $JMC = 0.9$ sustains its shear wave splitting of 5.4% up to the higher stress of 25 MPa. However, the subsequent drop of splitting parameter after 25 MPa is quite abrupt. At 35 MPa, the splitting parameter falls below 1% to as low as 0.7%. The stable residual values of splitting parameter suggest that the splitting effect is negligible after 35 MPa.

The shapes of these data curves create an awareness that the entire splitting behavior can be analyzed by dividing into three stages. The first stage is recognized as the initial drops of splitting parameter up to approximately 10 MPa. The second stage is defined as a stress range in which the splitting parameter keeps almost constant values. The matched fracture sample having $JMC = 0.9$ remains this stage up to 25 MPa. In $JMC = 0.1$ case, the second stage ends at 20 MPa. The beginnings of third stage are observed as the second significant decrease in splitting parameter. In the data curve of matched fracture sample having $JMC = 0.9$, the third stage beginning at 25 MPa suddenly ends at 35 MPa. The most-mismatched fracture sample enters its third stage at 20 MPa but the end of stage is not clear. The intermediately-mismatched fracture sample having $JMC = 0.3$ presents an in-between stress dependency. In the first stage up to 12 MPa, the average tangential slope of splitting parameter of this sample is observed to be intermediate between the samples having $JMC = 0.9$ and 0.1. Defining clearly the second

stage for this sample is difficult, but it may be recognized as a stress range from 12 to 16 MPa. In the third stage seen after 16 MPa, the stress sensitivity of splitting parameter is intermediate between the matched and most-mismatched

3.2 Model for stress and shear displacement shear wave splitting

The experimental results of the shear wave splitting tests shown above indicate that the shear wave splitting becomes pronounced as the *JMC* increases and decreases with increasing effective stress. For the observed dependency of shear wave splitting, the following simple model is proposed:

$$SSP = SSP_0 \cdot \exp \left\{ - \left[\left(\frac{\sigma'_n}{\sigma_0} \right)^n \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

where *SSP* is shear wave splitting parameter, *SSP*₀ is a non-dimensional material parameter giving the *SSP* value at zero normal stress condition, σ'_n is the effective normal stress acting on the fracture, σ_0 is a curve-fitting parameter in stress unit, which specifies the stress value where the *SSP* value decreases to 36.8% of its initial value, and *n* is a non-dimensional curve fitting parameter. In this study, the effective normal stress on fracture joint is substituted with the effective confining stress given as $P_{eff} = P_c - P_{pore}$. Figure 11 shows that the strong stress dependency of splitting parameter observed at the lower stress ranges for the fractured core samples having *JMC* = 0.3 and 0.1 is sufficiently described by the proposed model with *R*² values of 0.957 and 0.885, respectively. For the matched fracture sample (*JMC* = 0.9), the model sufficiently describes the beginning of third stage at 25 MPa followed by the abrupt drop of splitting parameter as well as the sudden end of this stage at 35 MPa. Table 1 summarizes the material parameter values to compute the model curves in this figure. The three fitting parameters are determinable from a simple curve fitting. The model proposed as Eq. (4) is

demonstrated to describe the observed significant changes in the stress sensitivity of shear wave splitting behavior of tested sandstones due to shear displacement in the wide-ranging effective stress. The model is useful because of its flexibility with only three parameters, although the physical meanings of the fitting parameters are not clear.

The fracture wave velocity increases with contact stiffness of the fracture joint (Pyrak-Nolte et al. 1992; Roy and Pyrak-Nolte 1995). This is because the normal contact stiffness increases with effective normal stress acting on the fracture joint (Bandis et al. 1983; Barton et al. 1985; Pyrak-Nolte et al. 1992; Katsuki et al. 2014; Almrabat et al. 2012). However, the magnitude of the normal stress effect on the should not be equal between the joints with different *JMC*. The normal contact stiffness is assumed to be higher as the degree of fracture mismatch increases. This is because the macroscopic normal stress must be converted to higher contact forces in fracture joint increasing in the degree of mismatch due to the smaller contact area.

As explained by using Eq. (3), when the specific stiffness is lower, shear wave splitting can be more enhanced. The smaller contact area on mismatched joint surfaces leads higher specific fracture stiffness due to higher stress concentration. Thus, the stress sensitivity of shear wave splitting behavior of mismatched joint is expected to be greater than that of matched joint. The stress sensitivity of the observed splitting–stress curves seen in Figure 10 consistently increases as the *JMC* decreases when the effective stress is less than 10 MPa. The reverse of stress sensitivity of splitting–stress curve subsequently observed after 25 MPa suggests that the contact force is distributed more uniformly due to formation of new contact area on the mismatched joint surfaces.

Figure 12 shows the shear wave splitting parameter curves with an effective stress parameter normalized by the Joint wall Compressive Strength (*JCS*). The normalized stress, P_{eff}/JCS , is multiplied by the coefficient, $1 - JMC$. The contact force intensity coefficient, $1 -$

JMC , reflects the stress-contact force conversion effect on the normal stiffness. As seen in Fig. 12, the splitting parameter gradually decreases when $x = (1 - JMC)P_{eff}/JCS < 0.03$ regardless of the degree of joint mismatching. Subsequently, the splitting parameters begin to decrease abruptly in the semi-logarithmic plot. The data curves of mismatched joint samples entirely coincide over the tested stress range. Interestingly, the shear wave splitting of these samples is likely to disappear at $x \approx 1$. The matched joint shows different stress dependency after the transition point of $x = 0.03$. This suggests that better forms should be considered as the contact force intensity coefficient $1 - JMC$ based on the micromechanics view point.

Although not directly investigated here, the effect of the Joint wall Compressive Strength (JCS) on splitting behavior can be discussed by reviewing the comprehensive study carried out by Bandis et al. (1983). Degradation of JCS is usually caused by weathering. They tested compared the normal deformation behaviors of fracture joints different in the degree of weathering. As the normal stress increases, the joint surfaces deform and the actual contact area expands. The effect of JCS should be observed as the stress sensitivity of expansion behavior of contact area. Actually, it was observed that the normal deformation of weathered joint was significantly larger than that of fresh fracture joint. They also reported that the actual contact area between the walls ranged between approximately 40% to 70% of the total sample area, depending on JCS and JRC despite the very high stress applied. The stress sensitivity of shear wave splitting is considered to be higher at lower JCS due to higher compressibility of fracture asperity.

The stress sensitivity of fracture aperture is considered to depend mainly on the normal fracture stiffness and the strength of joint wall as discussed above. In a mismatched fracture, the shear stiffness may play an important role in modeling the fracture aperture change due to the presence of contact shear force generated at mismatched contacts, but it is ignored in this study for the sake of simplicity.

4. Effects of Fracture Matching and Stress on Joint Rock Permeability

Figure 13 shows the stress dependent permeability of the intact and fractured core samples. As expected, permeability decreases with increasing effective stress particularly for the fractured samples and less so for the intact sample. The permeability of the intact sample at 1 MPa is 22.6 mD, and decreases asymptotically to 19.3 mD at 55 MPa. The permeability of fractured core sample with $JMC = 0.9$ decreases at the higher rate compared to that of intact core. For this core sample, the effect of fracture on the permeability disappears when the effective stress is higher than 10 MPa. The initial permeability of fractured rock cores increases with decreasing JMC values, which is expected as the fracture is more dilated when the fracture surfaces are initially unmatched. The relationship between the degree of stress dependency of permeability and JMC can be seen in this plot. The slope of the $k - P_{eff}$, where $P_{eff} = P_c - P_{pore}$, plot which corresponds to the decline in permeability with increasing stress appears to increase with decreasing JMC value. The main mechanism of permeability reduction of fractured rock due to effective stress increase should be the closure of fracture joint as modeled in the parallel plate model:

$$k = \frac{d_{eh}^2}{12} \quad (5)$$

where k is permeability and d_{eh} is the equivalent smooth wall hydraulic aperture. However, with increasing mismatch between fracture asperities, damage of the asperities and gouge formation increases, and as result fracture permeability increases as JMC decreases. Figure 14 shows a photograph of the fracture surfaces, before and after the test, for the sample with $JMC = 0.1$ showing the damage to the asperities and gouge formation after the fracture has been loaded.

Figure 15 plots the data of stress-dependent permeability of fractured sample, k_F , normalized by the intact sample permeability, k_I . The initial values of permeability ratio, k_F/k_I

of single fractured samples with $JMC = 0.9, 0.3,$ and 0.1 are $k_F/k_I = 1.9, 6.8,$ and $14.3,$ respectively. The effective stress shown in x -axis is normalized by the Joint wall Compressive Strength (JCS). The figure shows that the normalized permeability is insensitive to the stress up to the stress points indicated with the vertical arrows. After these points, the permeability begins to decline significantly. The values of transitional stress points for $JMC = 0.9, 0.3,$ and 0.1 are $P_{eff}/JCS = 0.043, 0.130,$ and $0.087,$ respectively.

The values are distributing in a relatively small value range from 0.04 to 0.13 . However, the magnitude of transitional state value has no correlation with the JMC values. It is interesting that the data curves of mismatched fracture samples after the transitional points converge coincide when $P_{eff}/JCS > 0.27$. These curves seem to converge finally at a physically meaningful point given as $(k_F/k_I, P_{eff}/JCS) = (1.0, 1.0)$.

To find out the physical meaning of permeability transitional stress point, the effective stress is further normalized by using JMC as shown in Figure 16. The normalization coefficient is arranged in the form of $(1 - JMC)^{-1}$ to reflect the effect of magnification in contact force due to decrease in contact area caused by joint mismatching as shown in Fig. 14. Using the coefficient $(1 - JMC)^{-1}$ is expected to normalize this contact force magnification effect. It is seen that the degree of coincidence in the declining curves in the post-transition point between the mismatched fracture samples becomes more significant. An extrapolation of the post-transition curves seems to merge around a physically interesting point given as $(x = P_{eff}/[(1 - JMC) \cdot JCS], y = k_F/k_I) = (1.0, 1.0)$. More interestingly, the post-transition curve of matched fracture with $JMC = 0.9$ also coincides with the dotted line given by $k_F/k_I = 1.0$ at $x = 1$. These behaviors indicate that the introduced stress magnification coefficient, $(1 - JMC)^{-1}$, is useful to normalize the effect of stress concentration on hydraulic aperture behavior.

An empirical model of the post-transition stress-dependent permeability of fractured samples is proposed as follows:

$$\frac{k_F}{k_I} = 1 + k_0 \cdot \exp \left\{ - \left[\left(\frac{P_n}{P_0} \right)^m \right] \right\} \quad (6)$$

$$P_n = \frac{\sigma'_n}{(1-JMC) \cdot JCS} \quad (7)$$

where k_0 is a non-dimensional fitting parameter representing the permeability ratio value given as $k_0 = k_F/k_I (\sigma'_n = 0) - 1$, P_n is the normalized stress parameter, P_0 is a dimensionless fitting parameter, and m is a fitting parameter. Fitting of Eq. (6) carried out for the test data seen in the post-transition states determines the material parameter values as $k_0 = 345.1$, $P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$, and $m = 0.263$. The model is observed to be capable of describing sufficiently the post-transitional behavior of the fractured samples. The model has a relatively simple form consisting of two curve-fitting parameters and a normalized stress parameter with a clear in physical meaning.

The relationship between the permeability of fractured rocks and the splitting behavior should be great interest for technological development to remotely detect permeability changes in deep reservoirs due to fracturing. Figure 17 plots the relationship between the normalized permeability and shear wave splitting parameter SSP in % multiplied by coefficient $1 - JMC$. It is observed that the permeability linearly increases with the value of $(1 - JMC) \cdot SSP$. The best fitting linear function with the intercept fixed at $y = 1$ is determined as

$$\frac{k_F}{k_I} = 1 + 1.991(1 - JMC)SSP \quad (8)$$

where SSP is given in percent. The R^2 value for this fitting result is 0.767 indicating a good agreement is observed between the fitting equation and the observed data.

The physical meaning of Eq. (8) can be understood as follows. The value of splitting parameter SSP itself includes the effect of contact stress intensity due to joint mismatching. This is obvious from Figure 12 showing the nearly-unique splitting behavior normalized by the stress intensity coefficient $1 - JMC$. Thus, multiplication of splitting parameter by the

coefficient $1 - JMC$ to form $(1 - JMC) \cdot SSP$ can develop SSP to be a parameter including the effect of joint mismatching on hydraulic aperture. The coefficient value becomes higher as the degree of mismatching increases. Rigorous discussion on detailed mechanism of the normalization cannot be currently provided due to limitation of further micromechanics properties of fracture surfaces. However, the good agreement shown in Figure 17 suggests that shear wave splitting and JMC are useful parameters capable of estimating permeability of fractured rocks.

5. Conclusions

The stress and shear displacement dependencies of shear wave splitting and permeability of fractured sandstone were tested by using a high pressure triaxial cell. To the Authors' knowledge, this is the first systematic experimental study on the effect of joint mismatching on shear wave splitting behavior. The cylindrical core samples of Berea sandstone were artificially fractured by inducing tensile stress along their longitudinal axis similar to a Brazilian Splitting Test. The induced fractures were characterized by using profilometer and tilt test. The induced fractures were highly reproducible with JRC values in a narrow range of 6.5 ± 0.1 . To investigate the effects of joint mismatching on shear wave splitting and permeability, different levels of joint shear displacements were applied to the fractured core samples. The JMC values were determined to be 0.9, 0.3, and 0.1 for fractured core samples having 0, 0.45, and 1.00 mm of joint shear displacement, respectively. Shear wave splitting is measured at effective confining stresses varying from 2 to 55 MPa.

Contrary to expectations, the initial values of shear wave splitting parameter observed at 2 MPa of effective stress are insensitive to the initial shear displacement. The values are approximately 7% regardless of the initial shear displacement. The splitting parameter decreases with effective stress and finally becomes almost zero in the matched joint sample.

The stress effect on the splitting parameter varies depending on JMC value. The effective stress at which the splitting disappears increases with decreasing JMC value. Interestingly, the stress sensitivity of splitting parameter at lower stress level less than 25 MPa becomes higher as the degree of joint mismatching increases. After 25 MPa, the stress sensitivity of splitting of matched joint sample suddenly increases and the splitting value abruptly drops to nearly zero value at 40 MPa. The shear wave splitting observed was modeled as a monotonically decreasing function of effective stress as quite simple function of normal stress conditioned with three fitting parameters. Good agreement was observed between the observed data and model by fitting only set of model parameters for the different JMC and effective stress values.

The stress dependency of shear wave splitting is normalized by using JCS and JMC . The effective stress effect that causes fracture joint closure is normalized as $(1 - JMC) \cdot P_{eff} / JCS$. It was observed that the transition stress point from which significant degradation of shear wave splitting begins appears to be $(1 - JMC) \cdot P_{eff} / JCS = 0.03$ regardless of JMC value. The significant degradation of shear wave splitting after the transition is well normalized by $(1 - JMC) \cdot P_{eff} / JCS$ for the mismatched joint samples.

The permeability of fractured rock core samples is also strongly dependent on the effective stress. It is found that the permeability–stress curve normalized respectively by intact matrix permeability and the fracture mechanical properties given as $[JCS \cdot (1 - JMC)]^{-1} P_{eff}$ represents the observed stress dependent permeability behaviors of all fractured sandstone samples different in JMC . The proposed empirical model of stress-dependent fractured rock permeability well describes the post-transition permeability degradation with advantage of simplicity consisting of two curve-fitting parameters and a normalized stress parameter that has clear physical meaning.

Finally, the useful relationship between the fracture permeability and splitting parameter was found. The clear linear relationship is observed between the normalized

permeability and splitting parameter multiplied by $1 - JMC$. JMC is found to be useful material properties representing the fracture joint effects on both the shear wave splitting and permeability. The usefulness of JMC can be extended by combining with shear wave splitting.

Conflict of interest

We wish to confirm that there are no known conflicts of interest associated with this publication and there has been no significant financial support for this work that could have influenced its outcome.

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Figure captions

Fig. 1. Wave splitting in fractured rocks. A shear wave entering a vertically fractured medium is split into a fast (S1) component parallel to the fracture, and slow (S2) component perpendicular to the fracture (Martin and Davis, 1987).

Fig. 2. Macro-fractured core sample preparation: (a) fracturing core sample, (b) inducing artificial fracture shear displacement, and (c) finishing end surfaces.

Fig. 3. Typical joint surface profile of prepared core sample.

Fig. 4. Aperture and joint matching coefficient of macro-fractured core samples.

Fig. 5. A schematic of macro-fractured core sample placed in triaxial core holder. Arrows indicate directions of oscillation of compression (P), faster (S1) shear, and slower (S2) shear waves.

Fig. 6. Waveforms of faster (S1) and slower (S2) shear waves for macro-fractured core sample having $JMC = 0.1$ at 16 MPa of effective stress.

Fig. 7. Stress dependency of shear wave velocities of macro-fractured core sample having $JMC = 0.9$.

Fig. 8. Stress dependency of shear wave velocities of macro-fractured core sample having $JMC = 0.3$.

Fig. 9. Stress dependency of shear wave velocities of macro-fractured core sample having $JMC = 0.1$.

Fig. 10. Stress dependency of shear wave splitting parameter of macro-fractured core samples.

Fig. 11. Comparison of observed stress dependency of shear wave splitting parameter and proposed model curve.

Fig. 12 Shear wave splitting parameter curves with stress parameter normalized by JCS and JMC .

Fig. 13. Effective stress dependency of permeability of intact and macro-fractured rock core samples.

Fig. 14. Photograph of fracture surfaces for the test with $JMC = 0.1$ showing asperity damage and gouge formation due to fracture mismatch.

Fig. 15 Permeability–stress curves of fractured samples normalized with JCS .

Fig. 16 Permeability–stress curves of fractured samples normalized with JCS and JMC .

Fig. 17 Relationship between the fractured sample permeability normalized with intact rock permeability and shear wave splitting parameter multiplied by joint matching correction factor.

Table 1. Material parameter values of proposed model determined for fractured Berea sandstone core samples.

du_s^* (mm)	JMC	SSP_0 (%)	σ_0 (MPa)	n
0	0.9	6.28	31.16	3.941
0.45	0.3	8.47	16.23	0.712
1.00	0.1	27.94	0.388	0.202

* shear displacement applied to the fracture

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

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Fig. 11

Fig. 12

Fig. 13

Fig. 14

Fig. 15

Fig. 16

Fig. 17